

School of Medicine - University of Zagreb

Andrija Stampar School of Public Health

EUPHA – Public Mental Health Section

Croatian Institute for Brain Research

Croatian Psychiatric Association

Mental Health Association of South Eastern Europe

IN AND OUT OF YOUR MIND

6th Eastern-European Conference of Mental Health
&
3rd International Public Mental Health Conference

13 – 15 October 2022
Zagreb, Croatia

<https://inandoutconference.com>

ABSTRACT BOOK

SCHOOL OF MEDICINE - UNIVERSITY OF ZAGREB

CROATIAN PSYCHIATRIC ASSOCIATION

Andrija Štampar
School of Public Health

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EUPHA - PUBLIC MENTAL HEALTH SECTION

CROATIAN INSTITUTE FOR BRAIN RESEARCH

MENTAL HEALTH ASSOCIATION OF SOUTH-EASTERN EUROPE

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&
3RD INTERNATIONAL PUBLIC MENTAL HEALTH CONFERENCE**

IN AND OUT OF YOUR MIND

ZAGREB, CROATIA, 13 – 15 OCTOBER 2022

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REFLECTIVE CITIZENS IN CULTURAL SPACES - AVENUE TO STRENGTHEN MENTAL HEALTH (EXAMPLE OF NOVI SAD CAPITAL OF CULTURE 2022)

M Jevtic, I Flasar

Faculty of Medicine University of Novi Sad, Group Analytic Society Belgrade

Reflective Citizens workshops in Novi Sad started in 2014, in a multinational and specific multicultural environment, as supportive and open space for all citizens who wish to develop themselves, multiculturalism, tolerance and better social environment. Novi Sad became European Capital of Culture in January 2022, with a delay because of Covid pandemic. This global unexpected and long distraction is an additional reason to develop and nourish the Reflective citizens matrix. Specificity of Reflective citizens in Novi Sad (RCNS) is moving through cultural spaces and inclusion of children as equal partners in sharing dreams, thoughts and reflections. Reflective weekend (four different workshops Reflection through painting/drawing, Reflection on Health, Reflective Walk and Reflective dance), realized in April 2022, were an opportunity for exchanges of ideas, reflection, creativity and meeting of different generations. Social dreaming and free psychosocial associations in thinkrooms have defined topics: loneliness, helplessness, walls and borders, migrations, diversity, mental malnutrition, the presence of evil and the need for goodness, lack of communication, and also worry about children's future. RCNS have become the support and open space for all citizens who want to contribute to multiculturalism, tolerance, a better social environment, understanding the environment and building incentive bridges in communication through dialogue, positive cultural climate, building cultural capacities and fostering cultural dialogue through mutual reflection, thus contributing the quality of life. RCNS gives a contribution for improving mental health in the community through fostering dialogue and mutual reflection especially in important year when Novi Sad is European Capital of Culture.

INNOVATIONS IN TREATMENT OF PSYCHOSIS IN SOUTHEAST EUROPE

N Jovanovic

Queen Mary University of London, Wolfson Institute of Population Health, UK

Southeast Europe (SEE) is home to 70 million people living across 12 countries. These countries share similar socioeconomic background and tradition of healthcare systems, although many differences exist in the organisation of mental health care. The region has been called 'the blind spot on the global mental health map' due to lack of research and innovations delivered in mental health care services. In recent years European Commission has invested significant resources to improve mental health care of individuals with severe mental disorders in Southeast Europe. Two major, recently completed, projects are Recover-e and Impulse. This presentation will focus on findings from the Impulse study. We will start with an overview of evidence-based, non-pharmacological interventions for individuals with psychosis, with focus on what is offered and implemented in 12 SEE countries. Next, we will present key findings from the largest hybrid type II effectiveness-implementation psychosocial randomised-controlled trial ever conducted in SEE. We will show an evidence-based approach how to improve psychosocial aspect of treatment of individuals with psychotic disorders. Mental health services that offer a combined-therapy approach, including psychosocial interventions and pharmacotherapy, or offering psychosocial interventions as stand-alone treatment, can ensure holistic care, which is acceptable to patients and clinicians. We will discuss how to ensure that improvements and changes seen in the Impulse study are sustainable after the research project/funding ends.

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